

Supporting information

S1 Raw images of the original western blot images on the PVDF membrane (Merck, MA, USA), staining with Immobilon Forte Western HRP substrate (WBLUF0100 Merck Millipore, MA, USA) and detected by Amersham TM Image Quant 800 (Cytiva, MA, USA).

Standard protein ladder for western blot used Blu10 Plus (BLUltra) Prestained Protein Ladder (1BHC-PMB01-0500 BLUltra protein ladder, BIO-HELIX, Beining Rd, Keelung City, Taiwan)(M.W. from 6.5 to 270 kDa).

Supporting information

- Nrf2

Supporting information

- IRS-1

Supporting information

• pAKT/AKT

